

FEATURES OF NEUROLOGICAL COMPLICATIONS AFTER KOVID 19 INFECTION

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Abstract. This article provides information about the COVID-19 disease based on statistics and research.

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The main part. During the Covid-19 pandemic, neuropsychological symptoms are one of the most common manifestations of the disease itself, as well as the post-COVID syndrome. A typical emotional response to confirmation of a COVID-19 diagnosis is feelings of regret, indignation and irritation, as well as signs of anxiety with possible panic attacks, phobias, insomnia and depression. Poor sleep (dyssomnia) leads to a decrease in working capacity, a deterioration in mood, concentration and quality of life. At the same time, many authors have noted that about $\frac{3}{4}$ of patients who recovered from COVID-19, after being discharged from the hospital, suffer from at least one of such neuropsychological disorders as anxiety, depression, asthenia, or sleep problems over the next six months. Quality sleep is an important component of mental health, necessary for the formation of memory, attention, maintenance of activity during the day and of course the functioning of the immune system.

The purpose of the study: to assess the types of psychoneurological disorders in COVID-19 and develop ways to correct them.

Materials and methods: In order to assess the quality of life, a study was conducted on 45 covid-infected patients in the acute and post-cavin period. The mean age of the patients was 45.1+3 years. Gender distribution: men 25 (55%), women 20 (45%)

All patients underwent a thorough neurological and neuropsychological examination. To assess the quality of life, a differentiated questionnaire was used that takes into account the multisystem nature of Covid-19, including 47 questions aimed at identifying the main symptoms of the disease in accordance with the nature of the disorders and the course of this infection and determining the degree of social adaptation of the patient. Grouping of questions was carried out as follows: 3 questions on the condition of the skin, 5 questions on the gastrointestinal tract, 6 questions on the cardiovascular system, 5 questions on blood circulation in the limbs, 6 questions on the sense organs, 1 question on sexual function, 5 questions on the psychological characteristics of the individual, 12 questions on the social aspects of adaptation and satisfaction with medical care, 4 questions on the state of sleep. There were three possible answers for each question; 1st - 0 points (practical absence of symptoms without affecting the course of the patient's life); 2nd - 1 point (periodic, moderate impact on the course of the patient's life with a decrease in activity); 3rd - 2 points (pronounced manifestation of symptoms and a sharp decrease in vital activity).

Results and discussion. An analysis of the examinations performed in covid-infected patients in the acute period of infection revealed the prevalence of the following symptoms: confusion (28%), mood disorders (33%), memory impairment (34%), anxiety (36%), sleep disorder (42%).

At the same time, the leading symptoms of the postcavid period were the following: psychological characteristics of the personality, such as working life and opportunities in relation to work - 18%, physical ability to do something - 56%. The above signs were manifested by such complaints as weakness, deterioration of sleep, memory, concentration of attention against the background of low mood.

Thus, sleep disturbance is one of the leading manifestations of both acute coronavirus infection and post-covid syndrome. According to the Oxford study by Y.F.Lo et al (2021), 20% of people who recover from Covid-19 have mental disorders for 90 days or more.

Based on our own observations and supervision of patients in the intensive care unit with Covid-19, we have identified a special type of anxiety - "fear of falling asleep". This condition has found a connection with such factors as: the patient's fear of "not waking up", the fear of being transferred to another department or being discharged from the hospital, constant thoughts about a catastrophe with one's own health ("catastrophization effect"), overestimation of one's own symptoms (hypersensitivity to body signals), fear of being alone, demonstration by the patieparadoxical effect of the level of oxygen saturation of capillary blood in the state of "sleep / wakefulness" - during sleep, blood saturation increases.

In the post-cavid period, patients also observed a change in the content of dreams - their emotional component significantly increases, and feelings of fear, anger, helplessness, anxiety, and persecution predominated.

Research by N. Kim (2020) showed the following results: an increase in sleep duration of only 1 hour reduces the likelihood of COVID-19 disease by 12%, while daytime sleep by 6%. At the same time, any sleep disturbances correlate with an increase in COVID-19 infections. It has also been noted that good sleep quality prior to vaccination is an important immunomodulatory factor.

Thus, in the treatment of neuropsychiatric complications in the acute stage of COVID-19 or the post-COVID period, it is necessary to use means that affect not only the process of falling asleep, but also the prevention of the development of nightmares (night terror).

In two groups of patients studied, the following therapy was carried out: in the first, main group, SSRI preparations with the addition of PasiValem 5 HTP were recommended against the background of basic therapy; in the second group, the comparison group, patients received basic treatment with the inclusion of tranquilizers. When comparing the results of treatment, the following indicators were identified. In the main group, taking Escitalopram at a dosage of 10 mg once a day in the morning for 1 month and PasiValem 5 HTP 1 tablet in the evening for 1 month gave significantly better indicators of changes in psychoneurological status. Symptoms such as mood disturbance, anxiety, sleep disturbance improved in 98% of patients. Whereas when using tranquilizers, such side effects were found accompanying patients, such as hypersedation, excessive muscle relaxation, "behavioral toxicity" (impairment of cognitive functions and psychomotor skills), paradoxical reactions (increased aggressiveness and agitation, sleep disturbances, mood deterioration), the formation of mental and physical addiction. Thus, the side effects of tranquilizers often exceed their therapeutic effect on improving the quality of sleep.

Studying the pharmacokinetics of Escitalopram, we made the following conclusions: the peculiarity of clinical efficacy is associated with a double effect of the drug - on the primary and allosteric sites; early antidepressant effect (3-4 days); balanced effect - gives significant results both with anxiety and agitation, and with apathy and lethargy; lack of somatotoxicity - no effect on blood pressure, heart rate, ECG; lack of behavioral and cognitive toxicity; stimulation of neuroplasticity (production of MNF, MSB, sprouting). Due to the dual mechanism of action, Escitalopram relieves patients from anxiety, vegetative and asthenic manifestations. The addition of PasiValem 5 HTP, 1 tablet per day, preferably 30 minutes before bedtime, in combination with Escitalopram, gives a significantly significant improvement in both the somatic and neuropsychiatric

state of patients. At the same time, thanks to a rational combination of components and an increased dose of valerian, each subsequent use, each tablet becomes more effective than the previous ones. There is an effect of filling the action - 30 tablets will be much more effective than the first. Therefore, it is better to use PasiValem 5 HTP not once, but as a course - within a month - for a long-term improvement in sleep, rest and mood, which is especially important for post-covid patients, since they have a long-term sleep disturbance - up to 6 months.

Summing up, we can say that quality of sleep is an important component of human mental health, necessary for the formation of memory, attention, maintenance of activity during the day and the functioning of the immune system. A safe, effective and affordable alternative to the overuse of tranquilizers for the treatment of sleep disorders is the combination of SSRIs and the herbal preparation PasiValem 5. The result of using this combination is not only the normalization of sleep, calming, but also what is very important - an improvement in morning vigor, an increase in mood and performance throughout the day, and a decrease in fatigue.

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